

Analysis of the Key Drivers Behind the Increasing Demand for Evaluation in West Africa

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ABSTRACT

Despite the growing institutionalization of monitoring and evaluation (M&E) systems across Africa, limited attention has been given to the factors driving evaluation demand in West Africa. This study examines the key drivers shaping demand for evaluation and their implications for the region's evaluation systems. Using a mixed-methods approach, the study draws on literature, policy documents, institutional reports, and survey data from 230 development practitioners across 14 West African countries.

Findings show that evaluation demand is influenced by both external accountability pressures and internal governance and learning needs. Donor requirements emerged as the strongest driver, with 91% of evaluations linked to donor expectations, followed by accountability and transparency demands, alignment with international standards, evidence-based decision-making, organizational learning, and professionalization processes.

The study also identifies a gradual shift from donor-driven, compliance-oriented evaluation toward a more institutionalized evaluation culture marked by stronger government engagement, expanding professional networks, improved evaluation capacity, and increasing use of evidence in decision-making. The study contributes an integrated framework for understanding evaluation demand in West Africa.

1. Introduction and background

Over the past two decades, evaluation has emerged as an increasingly important component of governance, public policy, and development practice across Africa. Governments, development partners, civil society organizations, and international non-governmental organizations are placing greater emphasis on the systematic assessment of policies, programs, and projects to determine their effectiveness, efficiency, relevance, sustainability, and impact. This growing interest reflects a broader global shift toward results-based management, evidence-informed policymaking, accountability, and learning. In West Africa, where governments and development actors continue to confront complex socio-economic challenges, including poverty reduction, food insecurity, unemployment, governance reforms, climate vulnerability, and service delivery constraints, the demand for credible evidence to inform decision-making has become increasingly important. Evaluation is therefore no longer viewed solely as a donor compliance requirement but is increasingly recognized as a strategic tool for improving development effectiveness and strengthening governance systems.

Despite the growing prominence of evaluation in the region, the factors responsible for the increasing demand for evaluation remain insufficiently examined in the literature. Existing studies have largely focused on evaluation capacity development, national monitoring and evaluation systems, evidence-informed policymaking, and the institutionalization of evaluation within governments. While these studies acknowledge the expansion of evaluation activities across Africa, limited attention has been paid to the systematic identification and analysis of the specific drivers of this growth, particularly in West Africa. Furthermore, much of the available literature tends to examine individual countries or isolated aspects of evaluation demand, leaving a gap in understanding

how multiple political, institutional, donor, governance, and professional factors collectively influence the demand for evaluation across the sub-region. This gap limits the ability of policymakers, development practitioners, and evaluation professionals to design strategies that effectively respond to the evolving evaluation landscape.

The increasing demand for evaluation raises several important questions. What factors are driving organizations and governments to commission more evaluations than in the past? To what extent are donor requirements, accountability concerns, globalization, evidence-based decision-making, organizational learning, professionalization, capacity development, and government regulations shaping this demand? More importantly, what do these trends imply for the future development of evaluation systems and evaluation practice in West Africa? Addressing these questions is particularly important because understanding the drivers of demand is essential for strengthening both the utilization and sustainability of evaluation systems. Without a clear understanding of why demand is increasing, investments in evaluation capacity development, institutionalization efforts, and professionalization initiatives may fail to adequately address stakeholders' actual needs.

Against this background, the primary objective of this study is to identify and analyze the key drivers contributing to the increasing demand for evaluation in West Africa and to examine how these drivers are influencing the evolution of evaluation systems and practices in the region. Specifically, the study seeks to assess the state of evaluation demand and supply, explore the relative influence of major demand drivers, and examine the implications of growing evaluation demand for governance, accountability, organizational learning, capacity development, and sustainable development outcomes. By synthesizing evidence from literature and practitioner perspectives across multiple West African

countries, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of the forces shaping the region's evaluation ecosystem.

This study contributes to the ongoing discourse on evaluation in Africa in several ways. First, it provides one of the few region-wide analyses focused specifically on the drivers of evaluation demand in West Africa. Second, it expands existing discussions on evaluation capacity development and institutionalization by highlighting the interplay between external drivers, such as donor requirements and international standards, and internal drivers, including accountability needs, evidence use, organizational learning, and government policy reforms. Third, the study offers empirical insights from development practitioners across the region, thereby contributing contemporary evidence to debates on the future of evaluation systems in Africa. Finally, the findings provide practical implications for governments, development partners, evaluation associations, universities, and practitioners seeking to strengthen locally owned, sustainable, and utilization-focused evaluation systems that support the achievement of the SDGs and the African Union's Agenda 2063.

This paper uses comparative analysis of qualitative/quantitative data, including case studies and personal experiences, to show M&E applications/deviations. Data from practitioner reviews, project reports/evaluations, and West African anecdotes were analyzed using coding/thematic analysis to explore rising demand, its causes, and program impacts, informing future insights.

2. Definition of Key Terms

To mitigate the equivocation fallacy, keywords are defined or rephrased to avoid ambiguity.¹

2.1. Evaluation

Program evaluation assesses the overall value, strategies, and utility of a collection of projects, often deferred until projects are underway, with annual interim data. Project evaluation targets individual projects or critical components, checking goal achievement and contributions to success/failure.²

To OECD/DAC, evaluation is "an assessment, as systematic and objective as possible, of an ongoing or completed project, program, or policy, its design, implementation, and results. The aim is to determine the relevance and fulfillment of objectives, developmental efficiency, effectiveness, impact, and sustainability. An evaluation should provide credible and useful information, enabling the incorporation of lessons learned into the decision-making process of both recipients and donors." Evaluations involve identifying and reflecting upon the effects of what has been done and judging their worth. Their findings allow project/program managers, beneficiaries, partners, donors, and other project/program stakeholders to learn from the experience and improve future interventions.³

2.2. Demand and Supply of M&E

Demand for M&E refers to the desire and willingness of stakeholders, such as government agencies, donors, and other development partners, to seek and utilize M&E services and information to improve decision-making, ensure accountability, and enhance the effectiveness of programs and policies. This demand is often driven by the need for evidence-

¹ Anand Jayprakash Vaidya and Andrew Erickson, *Logic & Critical Reasoning: Conceptual Foundations and Evaluation Techniques* (Dubuque, IA: Kendall Hunt, 2011), 38–39.

² Patrick Gudda, *A Guide to Project Monitoring & Evaluation* (Bloomington, IN: AuthorHouse, 2011), 56.

³ International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies, *Project/Program Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) Guide* (Geneva, Switzerland: IFRC, 2011), 15.

based decision-making and the pressure to demonstrate results and accountability to funders and the public.⁴

Supply of Monitoring and Evaluation: M&E refers to the availability and provision of M&E services, including the human resources, methodologies, tools, and institutional frameworks needed to conduct evaluations and generate reliable data. The supply-side concerns include evaluators' capacity, the availability of relevant data, and the institutionalization of M&E systems within organizations and governments.⁵

3. Methodology

This study employed a mixed-methods review design that combined qualitative and quantitative evidence to examine the factors driving the increasing demand for evaluation in West Africa. The research drew primarily on secondary data sources, including peer-reviewed journal articles, policy documents, evaluation capacity assessments, reports from international development organizations, and empirical studies on M&E systems in Africa. In addition, the study incorporated findings from a regional assessment of 230 development practitioners across 14 West African countries conducted by the author, as well as evidence from existing literature on evaluation demand, supply, capacity development, governance, and evidence-informed policymaking. The use of multiple data sources enabled triangulation of findings and enhanced the credibility of the analysis.

The study adopted a purposive sampling approach for document selection. Sources were included if they focused on evaluation systems, monitoring and evaluation practices, evidence-based policymaking, accountability mechanisms,

donor influence, capacity development, or evaluation utilization in Africa, particularly in West Africa. Priority was given to publications produced by recognized institutions such as the World Bank, UNICEF, UNDP, OECD-DAC, AfrEA, CLEAR-AA, and peer-reviewed academic journals. The practitioner survey component relied on development professionals actively engaged in development programming, monitoring and evaluation, public policy, and related sectors across West Africa, thereby ensuring that participants possessed relevant experience and knowledge regarding evaluation practice in the region. The inclusion criteria required that documents and datasets provide evidence relevant to the demand for evaluation, its drivers, or factors influencing evaluation systems within the African context.

An analytical framework based on thematic and comparative analysis was employed to synthesize evidence from the selected sources. Qualitative information was coded and grouped into recurring themes representing the principal drivers of evaluation demand, including donor requirements, accountability and transparency, globalization and international best practices, evidence-based decision-making, organizational learning, capacity building, professionalization of M&E, and government policy requirements. Quantitative findings from practitioner surveys and existing studies were used to support and validate qualitative insights. Comparative analysis enabled the examination of patterns across countries and institutions, while triangulation of multiple sources strengthened the robustness of conclusions regarding the evolving evaluation landscape in West Africa.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the study relied heavily on secondary literature and practitioner

⁴ Keith Robin Mackay, *How to Build M&E Systems to Support Better Government* (Washington, D.C.: The World Bank, 2007), 6.

⁵ Jody Zall Kusek and Ray C. Rist, *Ten Steps to a Results-Based Monitoring and Evaluation System: A Handbook for Development Practitioners* (Washington, DC: World Bank, 2004), 24.

perceptions, which may introduce publication and respondent biases. Second, although the practitioner survey covered multiple countries, findings may not fully represent all contexts within West Africa. Third, variations in evaluation maturity, institutional capacity, and data availability across countries may affect the comparability of findings. Finally, language barriers and the limited availability of published evidence from some Francophone countries may have resulted in the underrepresentation of certain experiences and perspectives. Despite these limitations, the triangulation of diverse data sources and the inclusion of evidence from regional practitioners provide a credible basis for understanding the factors driving the growing demand for evaluation in West Africa.

4. State of Demand and Supply of Evaluation in West Africa

The demand for evaluation in West Africa has expanded considerably over the past two decades, reflecting broader global shifts toward evidence-informed policymaking, results-based management, and accountability in public governance. Evaluation demand may be actual, latent, or potential, depending on decision-makers' awareness of and capacity to use evidence. Demand is shaped by differing institutional priorities: executive branches often emphasize performance improvement and service delivery, while legislatures tend to focus on accountability and oversight. The literature consistently suggests that internally generated demand for evaluation, rather than donor-driven demand, enhances ownership, credibility, and utilization of findings. Consequently, understanding evaluation demand requires a political economy perspective that considers both formal institutional arrangements and informal political influences on the use of evidence.

Across Africa, governments and development partners have increasingly invested in national M&E systems to strengthen governance, accountability, and evidence-based decision-making. Often framed as evidence-informed policymaking, performance budgeting, or results management, these systems seek to integrate routine monitoring information with evaluation evidence to support policy formulation and resource allocation. However, the literature highlights a persistent gap between the establishment of M&E structures and their effective utilization. While monitoring functions have expanded rapidly, many systems remain compliance-oriented, emphasizing reporting requirements rather than organizational learning and adaptive management. As a result, evaluations frequently serve accountability purposes without fully realizing their potential to stimulate institutional learning and policy change.

On the supply side, evaluation capacity in Africa has grown substantially, challenging long-standing assumptions that high-quality evaluations must be led by researchers from Europe or North America. Evidence shows that at least 1,520 African researchers from 34 countries have contributed to impact evaluations, with African scholars serving as first authors in 13% of studies and exclusively African-authored teams producing 14% of publications. In West Africa, evaluation expertise is particularly concentrated in Benin, Burkina Faso, Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, Nigeria, and Senegal. Although language barriers and publication biases may underrepresent Francophone contributions, the identification of 337 researchers across 14 Francophone countries demonstrates a growing pool of local expertise.

These findings indicate that the challenge facing West Africa is increasingly not the absence of evaluators but rather the need to strengthen institutional mechanisms that enable local expertise to be systematically utilized and recognized.

Despite this progress, the literature identifies significant constraints that continue to limit the development of evaluation capacity. The growing demand for evidence-based decision-making has intensified the need for universities and professional institutions to train highly skilled evaluators capable of producing rigorous and contextually relevant evaluations. Yet capacity-building efforts have often lagged behind demand due to inadequate funding, limited institutional support, and weak incentives to use evidence. Similarly, while many African countries have established M&E frameworks, these systems often struggle to produce timely, relevant information for decision-makers. Low stakeholder demand for M&E information, coupled with inconsistent governmental commitment to institutionalizing evaluation, further weakens the link between evidence generation and evidence use.

Several countries' experiences illustrate both the progress and the limitations of the institutionalization of evaluation in West Africa. In Ghana, evaluation continues to be strongly influenced by external development partners, but initiatives such as the Joint Agenda for Strengthening Monitoring and Evaluation and Statistics seek to increase domestic ownership through sustainable financing, strengthened local institutions, and greater reliance on national evaluators. In Senegal, donor influence remains significant, yet important reforms, including the establishment of high-level evaluation structures, the promotion of results-based management, and the emergence of the professional association SenEval, have contributed to a more professional and locally grounded evaluation ecosystem. Nevertheless, evaluations in Senegal continue to be used more for accountability and control than for organizational learning. Similarly, Benin has experienced increasing demand for evaluation and growing local capacity, although the extent to which evaluation findings influence planning and budgeting

decisions remains uncertain. These examples suggest that while institutional structures are emerging, the transition from evaluation production to evaluation utilization remains incomplete.

A notable feature of the West African evaluation landscape is the growing involvement of universities, voluntary organizations for professional evaluation (VOPEs), parliamentarians, civil society organizations, and development partners in strengthening evaluation culture. National evaluation associations now exist in most countries, while postgraduate programs in Monitoring and Evaluation have expanded significantly across African universities. The increasing number of academic publications, professional conferences, workshops, and practitioner networks demonstrates that evaluation has evolved from an emerging field into a recognized profession with a growing body of indigenous knowledge. This maturation is reflected in the expanding community of evaluators working across both public and non-public sectors and in the establishment of platforms such as the African Evaluation Journal that facilitate knowledge generation and dissemination.

Recent evidence also points to important shifts in the broader evidence ecosystem. Studies of the Evidence-Informed Policy (EIP) landscape highlight four interrelated trends: the strengthening of African research institutions, increasing emphasis on evidence intermediation rather than evidence production alone, growing attention to responsible data governance, and rising demand among policymakers for data and evidence. These developments reflect a gradual shift toward localization, in which African institutions play a more central role in generating, translating, and applying evidence in policy processes. Government champions, civil society advocacy, donor investments, and lessons from recent global

crises have all contributed to strengthening the culture of evidence use across the region.

Overall, the available evidence suggests that both the demand and supply of evaluation in West Africa are increasing. A regional survey of 230 development practitioners across 14 countries found that organizations conducted, on average, three more evaluations than they had five years earlier. Furthermore, 90% of respondents reported that evaluation activity had increased either significantly or moderately during the same period. These findings indicate growing recognition of evaluation as a strategic tool for accountability, learning, and decision-making. However, the literature also demonstrates that progress remains uneven. While evaluation capacity, institutional structures, and evidence ecosystems have strengthened considerably, challenges related to utilization, local ownership, sustainable financing, and institutional commitment continue to constrain the full realization of evaluation's transformative potential. Consequently, future efforts should focus not only on increasing the production of evaluations but also on strengthening demand for, utilization of, and nationally owned evaluation systems that support Africa's development aspirations, including those articulated in Agenda 2063.

5. Assessment of Evaluation Methods Used in Evaluations in West Africa

For evaluations to be effectively utilized by programs and policymakers, they must be credible in design, methodology, and recommendations. Since the primary purpose of evaluations is to inform decisions, facilitate learning, clarify options, reduce uncertainties, and provide critical insights into

programs and policies (Patton, 1986), the information obtained must be credible, valid, and usable. Selecting appropriate evaluation methods is essential to ensuring the findings are relevant and actionable, enabling better implementation of programs and policies.⁶

The assessment of evaluation methods used in West Africa reveals a diverse landscape of approaches, reflecting the region's complex developmental challenges and the evolving nature of evaluation practice. Traditional methods, such as quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews, remain prevalent, but there is a growing trend towards mixed-methods approaches that combine multiple data collection and analysis techniques. This shift is driven by the recognition that complex development interventions require a nuanced understanding, best achieved through methodological triangulation. Additionally, participatory evaluation methods have gained traction, aligning with the increasing emphasis on local ownership and contextualized knowledge in development practice. These evaluation methods face several challenges in the West African context. Resource constraints often limit the scope and rigor of evaluations, leading to compromises in sampling strategies and the depth of data collection. Cultural and linguistic diversity across the region necessitates careful adaptation of evaluation tools and approaches, a process that is not always adequately addressed.⁷

The review of 338 evaluation reports from the AfrED database reveals an increasing number of reports available after 2005, peaking in 2015, with more than half of them from 2015 onward. This trend might indicate a growing availability of reports as data was gathered or a rise in evaluations conducted over time.

⁶ Blaser Mapitsa, Tirivanhu, and Pophiwa, *Evaluation Landscape in Africa*, 2019, 113.

⁷ Michele Tarsilla, "Evaluation Capacity Development in Africa: Current Landscape of International Partners' Initiatives, Lessons Learned and the Way Forward," *African Evaluation Journal* 2, no. 1 (December 18, 2014): 4–11.

The study found that qualitative methods dominated the evaluations (55.6%), while quantitative methods were used in less than 10% of the studies. Among the 29 quantitative evaluations, randomized controlled trials and survey designs were the most common, accounting for 34.4% of quantitative methods, primarily in the health and education sectors, which are traditionally well-resourced for evaluation in Africa.⁸ It is often said that the "gold standard" method in evaluation is generally considered the Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT). However, it's important to note that while RCTs are highly regarded, they may not always be the most appropriate or feasible method for every evaluation context.

Many policy questions revolve around understanding cause-and-effect relationships, such as whether teacher training improves student test scores or if conditional cash transfer programs lead to better health outcomes in children. Impact evaluations are crucial for answering these questions by assessing the causal effects of programs on specific outcomes. Simply observing changes in outcomes after a program's implementation, such as an increase in a trainee's income following vocational training, does not establish causality, as other factors could be responsible for the change. Impact evaluations address this challenge by empirically determining how much a program alone contributes to the observed outcomes. These evaluations employ methods that rule out the influence of other factors, ensuring that the identified impact is genuinely attributable to the program being assessed.⁹ It is essential to continue improving the quality of evaluation approaches in West Africa.

6. Main Drivers Behind the Increasing Demand for Evaluation

6.1. Donor Requirement

Donor requirements are a primary driver of evaluation practices in West Africa, with international organizations and bilateral aid agencies mandating M&E frameworks as a condition for funding to ensure accountability and assess investment impact. This has created a strong evaluation culture across the region, as organizations adopt specific standards to meet donor expectations and secure continued support, a trend confirmed by a survey of 230 development practitioners, which found that donor requirements account for 91% of evaluations conducted in West Africa.¹⁰

A survey of 230 development practitioners revealed that 73% consider donor requirements to have a very great influence on the demand for evaluation in West Africa. Donors' growing emphasis on results-based management has further amplified this, pushing organizations to adopt robust evaluation methods, particularly in health, education, and agriculture, to demonstrate measurable outcomes. As a result, organizations are increasingly building internal evaluation capacities to align with donor expectations, secure future funding, and ensure the sustainability of their development projects.¹¹

Donor influence is pivotal in driving M&E efforts across Africa. Donor funding channels substantial money, resources, and expertise into African countries to conduct effective evaluations, strengthen M&E frameworks, and build the capacity of public-sector units to conduct their own

⁸ Caitlin Blaser Mapitsa, Precious Tirivanhu, and Nedson Popphiwa, eds., *Evaluation Landscape in Africa: Context, Methods and Capacity*, 1st ed. (AFRICAN SUN MeDIA, 2019), 131–33.

⁹ Paul J. Gertler et al., *Impact Evaluation in Practice*, Second Edition (Washington, DC: Inter-American Development Bank and World Bank, 2016), 60.

¹⁰ Tifuntoh, "Assessing the Growth of Evaluation in West Africa," 15.

¹¹ Tifuntoh, 15.

evaluations independently. This donor-driven focus raises essential questions about the appropriateness of evaluation methods and tools, advocating for an approach centered on African contexts and worldviews to ensure that evaluations are relevant to African realities.¹²

6.2. Accountability and Transparency

Growing pressure for accountability and transparency in governance and development is another key driver of demand for evaluation in West Africa. Governments and development agencies are increasingly expected to demonstrate the effective use of public funds, while the rise of democratic governance has further amplified citizens' and civil society's calls for greater transparency. This has led to the widespread adoption of M&E systems to track performance and outcomes. A report involving 230 development practitioners ranked accountability and transparency as the second-highest factor driving evaluation demand, with 79% of evaluations conducted to meet these needs.¹³

In West Africa, the focus on transparency is closely tied to anti-corruption efforts and improved governance, with evaluation serving as an objective tool to assess program implementation, identify inefficiencies, and address resource misuse. This promotes trust between governments, citizens, and donor agencies, driving the integration of evaluation into national development plans to bolster both domestic and international credibility. The adoption of international evaluation standards has further strengthened the role of evaluation in ensuring accountability and transparency across the region's

development efforts.¹⁴ Up to 74% of 230 development practitioners indicated that accountability and transparency have strongly influenced demand for evaluation in their organizations and across West Africa in the recent past.¹⁵

Effective M&E systems are essential for promoting government transparency and accountability, enabling governments to demonstrate progress toward development goals to stakeholders, including CSOs and donors. By disseminating findings through stakeholder forums and online platforms, these systems improve information accessibility and strengthen accountability, driving performance improvements in public institutions. In aid-dependent countries, they also ensure resources are used effectively under limited external oversight. Despite some implementation risks, the benefits, including greater public support and more informed decision-making, make results-based M&E systems a vital governance tool.¹⁶

M&E systems are increasingly recognized as vital tools for good governance, providing essential information on the relevance, efficiency, and effectiveness of government policies and programs. They strengthen public sector accountability, transparency, and learning while supporting evidence-based decision-making on development outcomes. Globally, M&E has become integral to public sector management, informing planning, budgeting, and resource allocation through tools such as performance monitoring, real-time evaluations, and audits. As a result, more countries are adopting M&E systems to meet growing expectations for accountable governance and poverty reduction, making them a cornerstone of modern

¹² Takunda Chirau, Ayabulela Dlakavu, and Banele Masilela, "Strengthening Anglophone Africa M&E Systems: A CLEAR-AA Perspective on Guiding Principles, Challenges and Emerging Lessons," *African Evaluation Journal* 10, no. 1 (April 28, 2022): 9.
<http://www.aejonline.org/index.php/AEJ/article/view/601>.

¹³ Tifuntoh, "Assessing the Growth of Evaluation in West Africa," 16.

¹⁴ Porter and Goldman, "A Growing Demand for Monitoring and Evaluation in Africa," 1.

¹⁵ Tifuntoh, "Assessing the Growth of Evaluation in West Africa," 16.

¹⁶ Kanyamuna, Alba Kotzé, and Phiri, "Monitoring and Evaluation Systems: The Missing Strand in the African Transformational Development Agenda," 9.

public sector management.¹⁷ These are some of the issues that are pushing up evaluation in West Africa.

6.3. The need to align with Globalization and International Best Practices

The third factor in the hierarchy among West African practitioners is aligning with Globalization and International Best Practices. This is the case for 71% of evaluations carried out in West Africa recently.¹⁸ The growing demand for evaluation in West Africa is also driven by the need to align with globalization and international best practices. As the region integrates further into the global economy, governments, NGOs, and development agencies are adopting internationally recognized evaluation standards to assess the effectiveness of their programs and policies. Aligning with these global norms enhances the credibility of development initiatives, ensures comparability with other regions, and is increasingly essential for attracting international funding, as donors require evidence of adherence to best practices before providing aid and investment.¹⁹

A survey of 230 West African development practitioners found that 73% consider the need to align with globalization and international best practices to be a strong influence on the demand for evaluation. This pressure has led to the institutionalization of evaluation systems within governments and development agencies, with many countries developing national evaluation policies that incorporate global standards such as the OECD-DAC criteria. This trend reflects a broader commitment to transparency, accountability, and results-

based management, helping West African countries improve governance and development outcomes while enhancing their competitiveness on the global stage.²⁰

A national M&E system is a comprehensive framework that guides M&E activities while building the capacity of individuals and institutions to use evidence for planning, policymaking, and decision-making. Its effectiveness depends on the institutionalization of M&E practices, supported by key components such as an M&E policy, defined methodologies, clearly assigned roles, capacity-building initiatives, stakeholder integration, and quality reporting. Evaluation Capacity Development is central to strengthening these elements by balancing the supply and demand for M&E evidence. In West Africa, demand for M&E is further stimulated by the development of M&E infrastructure, the formation of evaluation associations, and the empowerment of beneficiaries to assess development outcomes.²¹

6.4. Increased awareness of the importance of evidence-based decision-making

The third factor in the hierarchy among West African practitioners is Increased awareness of the importance of evidence-based decision-making. This is the case for 71% of evaluations carried out in West Africa recently.²² A growing awareness of the importance of evidence-based decision-making among governments, development agencies, and civil society organizations strongly influences the increasing demand for evaluation in West Africa. As these stakeholders recognize the critical role of reliable data and systematic

¹⁷ Kanyamuna, Alba Kotzé, and Phiri, 11.

¹⁸ Tifuntoh, "Assessing the Growth of Evaluation in West Africa," 17.

¹⁹ Ian Goldman et al., "The Emergence of Government Evaluation Systems in Africa: The Case of Benin, Uganda and South Africa," *African Evaluation Journal* 6, no. 1 (March 29, 2018): 6.

²⁰ Goldman et al., 4.

²¹ Chirau, Dlakavu, and Masilela, "Strengthening Anglophone Africa M&E Systems," 2.

²² Tifuntoh, "Assessing the Growth of Evaluation in West Africa," 18.

evaluations in informing policy and program decisions, there has been a marked shift towards integrating evaluation practices into planning and implementation processes. This shift is driven by the realization that decisions grounded in robust evidence are more likely to lead to effective and sustainable outcomes, particularly in addressing complex development challenges such as poverty, health, education, and governance. As a result, the demand for evaluation has surged, with policymakers and program managers seeking to use evaluation findings to guide resource allocation, refine strategies, and improve the overall impact of their interventions.²³

West African development practitioners noted that the extent to which the need to align with globalization and international best practices influences the demand for evaluation in their organizations and across West Africa is great (79% of the 230 practitioners who spoke on the subject).²⁴ Moreover, the increased emphasis on evidence-based decision-making has led to a culture change within regional organizations and institutions. As stakeholders become more familiar with the value of evaluations, there is a growing expectation that decisions should be supported by credible evidence rather than intuition or political considerations. This cultural shift is further reinforced by the growing availability of evaluation training and capacity-building initiatives, which equip local professionals with the skills to conduct high-quality evaluations.

The rise of evaluation networks and professional associations in West Africa has also contributed to this trend by promoting evaluation as a standard practice for decision-making. As awareness grows, the demand for evaluations that provide

actionable insights for evidence-based decision-making will likely remain a vital driver of the evaluation landscape in West Africa.²⁵

6.5. Organizational learning and improvement

According to practitioners, the fourth major cause of demand for evaluation in West Africa is fostering organizational learning and improvement. Organizations across the region, including government agencies, non-governmental organizations, and international development partners, realize that evaluations are tools for accountability and robust mechanisms for learning and continuous improvement. An assessment of 230 development professionals indicated that 69% of evaluations have increased as a result of Organizational Learning and Improvement. West African development practitioners noted that the extent to which the need to align with globalization and international best practices influences the demand for evaluation in their organizations and across West Africa is great (92% of the 230 practitioners who spoke on the subject).²⁶

M&E systems are expanding rapidly across Africa's public sector, sparking debates on their design and effectiveness. A central challenge identified is the heavy focus on compliance and monitoring, which often overshadows the strategic learning potential of evaluations. This tension raises questions about whether evaluations are used primarily to monitor outputs or to answer strategic questions that drive evidence-based decision-making. The diverse assumptions and expectations of stakeholders further complicate the evaluation process, leading to a potential mismatch between the intended and actual roles of evaluation in public-sector governance.

²³ Goldman et al., "The Emergence of Government Evaluation Systems in Africa," 5.

²⁴ Tifuntoh, "Assessing the Growth of Evaluation in West Africa," 18.

²⁵ Goldman et al., "The Emergence of Government Evaluation Systems in Africa," 6.

²⁶ Tifuntoh, "Assessing the Growth of Evaluation in West Africa," 19.

Despite the growing prominence of evaluation, the practice in Africa (especially in West Africa) remains largely donor-driven, raising concerns about the contextual relevance of evaluation methods and definitions of success. The chapter highlights the need for more empirical data to better understand the balance between monitoring and evaluation and its implications for governance, particularly regarding how evaluations inform programmatic strategies and public-sector reforms.²⁷

Feedback is a critical component of M&E processes, linking past activities to future ones and enabling organizational learning. Well-developed feedback loops are essential for using evaluation results to shape future policies and programs, thereby enhancing the sustainability and improvement of M&E systems and evaluations. Effective feedback mechanisms in evaluations promote institutional learning by prompting reflection on progress and adjustments to projects or programs as needed. They also serve as early warning systems that help identify and address potential problems in development interventions. However, sustaining the learning function of M&E is challenging due to the complex cultural, political, and bureaucratic dynamics within organizations. Despite these challenges, M&E remains a valuable management tool that supports informed decision-making and helps build learning organizations by improving the understanding of what works, what does not, and why.²⁸ This growing demand for Organizational Learning and Improvement drives organizations to request that they carry it out.

6.6. Increased capacity building and knowledge sharing

²⁷ Blaser Mapitsa, Tirivanhu, and Pophiwa, *Evaluation Landscape in Africa*, 2019, 28–31.

²⁸ Kanyamuna, Alba Kotzé, and Phiri, "Monitoring and Evaluation Systems: The Missing Strand in the African Transformational Development Agenda," 10–11.

The growing emphasis on capacity building and knowledge sharing within the region significantly influences the increasing demand for evaluation in West Africa. An assessment by development professionals indicated that capacity building and knowledge sharing ranked fifth among the main contributors to the region's increase in evaluation. The assessment indicated that 61% of practitioners reported that growth in Capacity building and knowledge sharing in their organizations drives the increase in demand for evaluation.²⁹ As governments, development organizations, and international donors recognize the importance of evidence-based decision-making, there is a parallel recognition that the region must develop its internal capacities to conduct high-quality evaluations. This need has driven substantial investments in training programs, workshops, and academic courses to enhance the skills of local evaluators and foster a community of practice around evaluation. These capacity-building efforts also increase the number of qualified evaluators in West Africa. Still, they also help create a knowledge base rooted in the local context, making evaluations more relevant and effective.³⁰

Moreover, the emphasis on knowledge sharing has become a critical driver for the demand for evaluation. As regional and international networks of evaluators expand, there is an increasing flow of information, best practices, and innovative methodologies across borders. This exchange of knowledge helps standardize evaluation practices in line with global standards while also allowing adaptation to the unique socio-economic contexts of West African countries. The collaborative nature of these networks fosters a learning

²⁹ Tifuntoh, "Assessing the Growth of Evaluation in West Africa," 20.

³⁰ Goldman et al., "The Emergence of Government Evaluation Systems in Africa," 2–10.

environment in which organizations can benefit from others' experiences, thereby improving the quality and impact of their evaluations. Consequently, the focus on capacity building and knowledge sharing is not only enhancing the technical capabilities of evaluators in West Africa. Still, it is also driving a culture of continuous improvement and innovation in evaluation practices across the region.³¹ Asked about how much capacity building and knowledge sharing have influenced the demand for evaluation in West Africa, 66% of 230 development practitioners in the region indicated that these activities strongly influence the increasing demand for evaluation.³²

Capacity building and knowledge sharing have significantly contributed to the increasing demand for evaluation in Africa. International development partners have played a crucial role in enhancing evaluation capacity by providing resources, training, and technical assistance to develop local expertise. Although often donor-driven, these efforts have established a more robust evaluation culture within African institutions, primarily through initiatives focusing on long-term, contextually relevant learning and systemic approaches. Despite challenges, including an emphasis on short-term training, there is growing recognition of the need for more sustainable, integrated capacity development strategies that are responsive to local contexts and needs, ultimately contributing to the broader goals of improved policymaking and governance in West Africa.³³

The history of capacity development in Africa, particularly in the context of Evaluation Capacity Development (ECD), has

been shaped by post-independence influences, including structural adjustment programs and the involvement of Bretton Woods institutions. Initially, capacity-building efforts were characterized by the transfer of skills from international experts to local counterparts, often reflecting Western development ideals. Despite increased capacity development initiatives and significant investments, including those by organizations such as the IMF and the African Capacity Building Foundation, a persistent gap remains between these efforts and the actual strengthening of evaluation practices on the continent. However, ECD remains essential for improving institutional evaluation capabilities, underscoring the need for ongoing research to identify effective capacity-development strategies.³⁴

Capacity in Western Africa is primarily concentrated in Benin, Burkina Faso, Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana, Nigeria, and Senegal. Although this region has fewer authors overall, interviews and surveys may have underestimated the capacity due to language barriers, particularly the predominance of French, which limits English-language publishing opportunities. Desk research revealed more capacity than initially expected, identifying 337 authors (of evaluations) across 14 countries by October 2019 (this trend has been improving gradually). This suggests that despite the challenges, there is a growing capacity for evaluation and research in Western Africa, though further exploration, particularly in Francophone countries, could reveal even more potential.³⁵

³¹ Goldman et al., 2–10.

³² Tifuntoh, "Assessing the Growth of Evaluation in West Africa," 20.

³³ Tarsilla, "Evaluation Capacity Development in Africa," 4–11.

³⁴ Candice Morkel and Neville Mangwiro, "Implications of Evaluation Trends for Capacity Development," in *Evaluation Landscape in Africa: Context, Methods and Capacity*, ed. Caitlin Blaser Mapitsa, Precious Tirivanhu, and Nedson Popihiwa, 1st ed. (AFRICAN SUN MeDIA, 2019), 6–7, <https://bit.ly/2NAovjj>.

³⁵ Altshuler and Staats, "A New Look at Impact Evaluation Capacity in Sub-Saharan Africa," 2.

6.7. Increased capacity building and the professionalization of M&E practices

The growing demand for evaluation in West Africa is driven in large part by increased capacity building and the professionalization of M&E practices. Only 57% of professionals across the region indicated that their increased evaluation is due to Increased Capacity Building and Professionalization around M&E. Professionals in the region ranked this factor as the sixth contributor to the demand for evaluation.³⁶ Over the past decade, concerted efforts by governments, development organizations, and international donors have significantly strengthened M&E capacity across West Africa. Through specialized training programs, academic courses, and certifications, the region has seen a growing pool of qualified M&E practitioners and improved evaluation standards that align with international best practices. This enhanced capacity has increased recognition of the value of evaluation, further driving demand across the region.³⁷

The professionalization of M&E in West Africa has been further advanced by the formation of professional bodies and networks, such as national evaluation associations and regional networks, that promote evaluation standards, ethical guidelines, and best practices and facilitate knowledge exchange among practitioners. This has enhanced the visibility and credibility of the M&E profession, leading to greater demand from governments, NGOs, and donors seeking skilled professionals to monitor and evaluate their programs. This trend is critical to sustaining evaluation growth in the region, as it builds local expertise and fosters a culture of

accountability and continuous learning within the development sector.³⁸ The African Evaluation Association (AfrEA) has seen growth in its membership of Voluntary Organizations for Professional Evaluators (VOPEs), indicating a rise in professional networks. Additionally, the sector is becoming more entrenched within higher education institutions, as evidenced by the African Evaluation Journal's accreditation. The professionalization agenda aims to enhance competencies, standards, and guidelines for evaluation practice, though consensus on these elements is still developing. This growth in capacity and professionalization is occurring alongside discussions about decolonizing knowledge and indigenizing evaluation approaches in Africa to better reflect local contexts and worldviews.³⁹

Academic M&E programs across African universities have expanded but continue to face challenges related to inadequate resources, infrastructure, and staffing, limiting their effectiveness in producing skilled graduates. The discipline also lacks a clear institutional home and is often scattered across departments without a unified focus, undermining its broader academic and professional influence. While the shift toward long-term academic courses reflects progress in building sustainable evaluation capacity, greater investment and strategic focus are still needed to fully realize these programs' potential and meet the region's growing demand for evaluation.⁴⁰

The formalization of evaluation as a profession remains debated, with concerns about credentialing's potential to disadvantage certain individuals or overlook the diversity of

³⁶ Tifuntoh, "Assessing the Growth of Evaluation in West Africa," 21.

³⁷ Goldman et al., "The Emergence of Government Evaluation Systems in Africa," 2–10.

³⁸ Porter and Goldman, "A Growing Demand for Monitoring and Evaluation in Africa," 2–10.

³⁹ Blaser Mapitsa, Tirivanhu, and Pophiwa, *Evaluation Landscape in Africa*, 2019, 165–77.

⁴⁰ Basheka and Byamugisha, "The State of Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E) as a Discipline in Africa from Infancy to Adulthood?" 13–14.

evaluation practices. Nevertheless, there is a growing push for professionalization across Africa, including West Africa, with academic institutions and organizations increasingly recognizing the need for standardized qualifications and competencies. Initiatives such as GIMPA's postgraduate M&E programs and CLEAR-AA's standardized curricula reflect this trend, driven by rising demand from governments and organizations. A broad consensus is emerging among African evaluators that establishing clear standards and competencies is essential to ensuring evaluator quality and advancing development goals across the continent.⁴¹

6.8. Increased requests or pressure from government policies and regulations

Development specialists in West Africa identified requests or pressure from government policies and regulations as the eighth factor driving up demand for evaluation. About 38% of the evaluation in West Africa is due to this factor.⁴² Over the past decade, many West African governments have recognized the importance of M&E in improving governance, enhancing transparency, and ensuring the effective use of public resources. As a result, several countries have integrated M&E requirements into their national development plans and policies, mandating the evaluation of government programs and projects. This regulatory push has created a more structured, formalized demand for evaluation, as public-sector entities are now required to demonstrate the impact and effectiveness of their initiatives. This governmental emphasis on accountability has also led to the establishment of dedicated M&E units within ministries and other government

agencies, further institutionalizing evaluation practice across the public sector.⁴³

Aligning national policies with international frameworks such as the SDGs has further amplified the demand for rigorous evaluations, as governments face growing pressure to report progress to both domestic and international stakeholders. This has fostered a more evaluation-conscious culture within government institutions, where evaluation findings increasingly inform policy decisions and resource allocation. Consequently, the demand for qualified evaluators and high-quality evaluations continues to rise, driven by the need to meet policy and regulatory requirements essential for maintaining public trust and government legitimacy.⁴⁴

The growth in demand for evaluation in West Africa is primarily driven by external accountability pressures and the institutionalization of results-based management, with donor requirements emerging as the dominant force. With 91% of evaluations linked to donor expectations and 73% of practitioners reporting very strong donor influence, evaluation in the region remains closely tied to funding relationships, in which evidence of effectiveness and accountability is a prerequisite for accessing development resources. While donor support has accelerated evaluation practice and capacity development, it has also raised concerns about the dominance of externally driven frameworks that may not always reflect African realities and priorities. The key challenge for West Africa is therefore not merely expanding evaluation activity, but ensuring that evaluation approaches remain

⁴¹ Laila R. Smith and Candice Morkel, "Trends in Supply and Demand for Evaluation in Africa: A View from CLEAR-AA," *eVALUation Matters*, March 2018, 6–7.

⁴² Tifuntoh, "Assessing the Growth of Evaluation in West Africa," 21.

⁴³ Goldman et al., "The Emergence of Government Evaluation Systems in Africa," 1–11.

⁴⁴ United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, "Sustainable Development Goals for the West Africa Subregion. Summary Report" (Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, 2015), 13–15.

contextually relevant and responsive to local development needs.

Closely linked to donor influence is a growing demand for accountability, transparency, and evidence-based governance, with 79% of evaluations conducted for accountability purposes and 74% of practitioners confirming that these considerations strongly influence the demand for evaluation. This reflects a broader governance shift in which evaluation is increasingly used to demonstrate performance, justify public expenditures, combat corruption, and improve decision-making, evolving from a compliance exercise into a strategic management tool. Globalization, evidence-based decision-making, organizational learning, and professionalization are further embedding evaluation into public-sector systems and organizational cultures. Collectively, these drivers point to a gradual transition from ad hoc evaluation practices toward a more institutionalized evaluation ecosystem in West Africa, where demand is increasingly sustained by governance needs, learning imperatives, and professional standards rather than donor requirements alone.

7. Impact of Increasing Demand for Evaluation

The growing demand to evaluate development projects in West Africa has significantly improved evidence-based decision-making and policy formulation. This heightened focus on evaluation has strengthened each of the identified pillars of public sector M&E systems. This positive trend increasingly shapes development planning, policymaking, and budgeting processes, guiding them with evaluative findings.

⁴⁵ Chirau, Dlakavu, and Masilela, "Strengthening Anglophone Africa M&E Systems," 2.

⁴⁶ Tebogo Fish et al., "Transforming Voluntary Organisations for Professional Evaluation into Central Pillars of National Evaluation Systems," *African Evaluation Journal* 10, no. 1 (July 12, 2022): 3, <https://doi.org/10.4102/aej.v10i1.608>.

This has fostered a culture of organizational learning and accountability, paving the way for a more effective and efficient evaluation landscape in West Africa.⁴⁵

The growing evaluation culture has sparked capacity-building initiatives across the region. VOPEs are experiencing membership growth, indicating a surge in professional evaluation networks. This expansion has led to more robust evaluation practices and methodologies tailored to West Africa. However, it's crucial to note that challenges persist. VOPEs in the continent are still having challenges in retaining members and getting members to participate in the execution or management of VOPE-related activities fully.⁴⁶ Addressing these challenges is urgent to ensure the sustainability and effectiveness of the evaluation landscape in West Africa.

The increased demand for evaluation has also spotlighted the need for Africa-centered approaches. Encouraging realist evaluation in health programs and other sectors can expand current evaluation approaches and bring more Africa-centered innovation.⁴⁷ This shift towards contextually appropriate methodologies creates a unique dynamic among program implementers, local stakeholders, and evaluators, transcending traditional boundaries between research and program practice and potentially leading to more relevant and impactful development interventions in West Africa.

West Africa's (especially Senegal's) rising demand for evaluation in development projects stems from donor policies, thereby boosting the role of evaluation in national processes.

⁴⁷ Susan Igras et al., "Realist Evaluation of Social and Behavior Change Interventions: Co-Building Theory and Evidence of Impact," *African Evaluation Journal* 10, no. 1 (November 21, 2022): 2, <http://www.aejonline.org/index.php/AEJ/article/view/657>.

Senegal excels in monitoring but lags in evaluation, largely tied to donor cycles, with few public policy assessments. Without centralized M&E, networks like SenEval advance supply/demand via capacity building. This underscores the need for context-specific, country-led systems with African roots (AfrEA projects, African Evaluation Journal). Indigenous practices and South-South cooperation are key to curbing donor dominance and enhancing ownership/utilization.⁴⁸

In general, the increasing demand for evaluation in West Africa has generated significant benefits for development effectiveness and public-sector performance. Evaluation is now used not only to assess whether programs achieve their intended outcomes but also to improve planning, implementation, and resource allocation. By providing credible evidence on what works, what does not, and why, evaluations enable governments, donors, and development organizations to make informed decisions and direct resources toward the highest-impact interventions. This evidence-driven approach has strengthened program effectiveness across sectors such as health, education, agriculture, governance, and poverty reduction, while also raising methodological standards by pushing evaluators toward more rigorous designs and clearer definitions of outcomes. In some sectors, particularly health and public policy, it has also created expectations for timelier evaluations to guide decisions when they matter most.

A further impact of the growing demand for evaluation is the strengthening of accountability, transparency, and good governance across the region. Evaluation findings increasingly provide citizens, policymakers, donors, and civil society with objective information on the performance of public policies and development initiatives, improving oversight of public expenditures and reducing opportunities for resource misuse.

The institutionalization of M&E systems within government structures has fostered a culture of performance management, in which evidence increasingly shapes decisions, alongside or instead of political considerations. Funders, governments, and partners now expect clear proof that resources are being used effectively, and evaluations are routinely used to determine whether programs should continue, expand, be redesigned, or discontinued. Consequently, evaluation has become a vital mechanism for promoting democratic governance, public trust, and responsible stewardship of national and donor resources.

The rising demand for evaluation has also accelerated professionalization and capacity development within the sector. Universities, training institutions, professional associations, and evaluator networks have expanded educational opportunities, certification programs, and knowledge-sharing platforms to meet the growing need for qualified evaluators, resulting in a larger pool of local professionals and stronger national evaluation systems. The growth of evaluation communities of practice has further facilitated learning, innovation, and cross-country collaboration, contributing to the emergence of a sustainable evaluation culture in the region. Overall, these developments have shifted evaluation toward a stronger focus on long-term impact and sustainability rather than immediate outputs alone, and are expected over time to strengthen national ownership of development processes, improve policy formulation, and support the achievement of regional priorities such as the SDGs and the African Union's Agenda 2063.

⁴⁸ Lomeña-Gelis, "Evaluation Development in Senegal," 7–8.

8. Conflict of Interest

The author states that there is no conflict of interest.

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